

INFLUENCE OF TEXTILE PARAMETERS AND LAMINATE BUILD-UP ON SURFACE QUALITY OF THERMOPLASTIC FIBER-REINFORCED COMPOSITES

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Keywords: *organic sheets, textile parameter, laminate build-up, waviness*

1 Influence of textile reinforcements

Due to the increasing challenge to alter the climate change the demand for sustainable development within several industries leads to the introduction of new processes and materials. Polymer composites like thermoplastic continuous fiber-reinforced composites, so called organic sheets, are promising candidates to help achieve this goal. A growing importance of these materials can be found in the automotive industry. However, when it comes to exterior applications tremendous efforts have to be made to meet the industries requirements, e.g. on the appearance of components. Due to the use of fabrics as reinforcing material in organic sheets, surface waviness occurs during the processing. The effect of various textile parameters on the surface waviness is not yet fully described in literature.

2 State of the Art and Objectives

Figure 1 shows a unit cell of an organic sheet with plain weave fabric reinforcement. In fabric reinforced composites there are matrix- and fiber-rich regions. The difference in the coefficients of thermal expansion (CTE) between matrix and reinforcement is typical in the range of one order of magnitude and the most important factor for the absolute waviness. During the processing stage, which includes a cooling step, the inhomogeneous fiber-matrix distribution leads to a typical waviness pattern on the components surface, which is dependent on various material and processing factors. The simplified cross-section A-A from Figure 1 provides a schematic of the geometry (see Fig. 2). The fiber cross-sections have been simplified from elliptical to circular shape as it only affects the shape but not the overall height of the waviness pattern. In real organic sheets there are usually matrix top layers of at least a few

micrometers. Therefore, a surface layer h_1 was included. The shrinkage Δd_F of the fibers plus surface layer and the shrinkage Δh_M of the matrix are calculated as follows.

$$\Delta d_F = d_0 \times \alpha_F \times \Delta T + h_1 \times \alpha_M \times \Delta T \quad (1)$$

$$\Delta h_M = h_0 \times \alpha_M \times \Delta T + h_1 \times \alpha_M \times \Delta T \quad (2)$$

Where d_0 and h_0 are the height of the roving and the matrix, respectively h_1 is the height of the surface layer, α_F and α_M are the coefficients of thermal expansion for the reinforcement and the matrix and ΔT is the maximum temperature difference that occurs during processing.

The maximum waviness is then derived as the difference between the two subsystems fiber rich region and matrix rich region.

$$W_z = \left| h_0 \times \alpha_M \times \Delta T + h_1 \times \alpha_M \times \Delta T \right| - \left| d_0 \times \alpha_F \times \Delta T + h_1 \times \alpha_M \times \Delta T \right| \quad (3)$$

As the shrinkage of the surface layer occurs in both subsystems equation 3 mathematically simplifies to

$$W_z = \left| h_0 \times \alpha_M \times \Delta T \right| - \left| d_0 \times \alpha_F \times \Delta T \right| \quad (4)$$

However, it should be noted that equation 4 does not consider any other effects e.g. interphase reactions, or polymer rheology of surface layers.

The effect of waviness creation which is commonly known as fiber print-through is well known in both the scientific and industrial community. Research led to various approaches to overcome the fiber print-through problem by the application of random fiber mats, unidirectional plies, gel coats or by combinations of these [3-6]. All of these approaches try to cover the underlying waviness.

Recent work also indicated a time dependent behavior of waviness creation, as aging of carbon fiber/epoxy composites in various liquids drastically increased waviness values [7].

A first theoretical approach to describe the phenomenon was introduced by Kia [8]. He set up a model for UD-reinforced thermoset materials that involves only thermal shrinkage in z-direction. It calculates the deformation as an integral of beam elements in which the stresses are induced due to thermal shrinkage. Blinzler used his approach to conduct further studies to evaluate material and process parameters on glass fiber-reinforced polycarbonate and polyamide organic sheets. The use of amorphous polymers reduces the waviness compared to semi-crystalline polymers, as there is no crystallinity shrinkage present. He additionally found out that an increasing stiffness of the surface layer improves waviness [10]. Other studies confirmed the positive effect of stiff surface layers but also found a critical stiffness area between 3-8 MPa with an increased surface roughness (see Fig. 3). A possible explanation states that softer materials act like a buffer while stiffer materials hinder deformation [5].

The influence of reinforcement architecture on surface waviness is not yet fully described. Further work of Kia concluded very little influence of single filaments with diameters between 10-20 μm on the surface structure [9]. Hochhalter et al. measured a highly increased roughness when changing the fiber diameter from 5 μm to 10 μm [11]. Furthermore, the type of reinforcement, whether it is made of glass, carbon or a different material, was found to have no influence on surface texture [10].

Most publications found deal with thermoset materials and describe possible solutions to decrease surface waviness by covering underlying waviness structures. There is little and sometimes not consistent data available on the effects of specific textile reinforcement parameters.

The scope of the paper is a quantitative study on the effect of specific textile parameters and laminate build-ups on the resulting surface quality of processed organic sheets.

14 different metal fabrics with variations in mesh size and fiber diameter are selected to evaluate a wide scale in the selected textile parameters. The use of metal fibers includes isotropic material properties and very constant and distinct fabric properties.

Furthermore, the thickness of the polymeric top layer is varied to evaluate the effect of local matrix culminations.

2 Experimental details

2.1 Materials and preparation

As matrix material an amorphous polycarbonate Makrolon® 2408 with one wt.-% carbon nanotubes is used. The nanotubes are used to blacken the otherwise transparent polycarbonate, which allows a better optical characterization. Previous trials showed no influence of the nanotubes on the optical properties of the composites. The material is supplied as films with a thickness of 100 μm .

The used reinforcement is a set of steel wire meshes supplied by Weisse & Eschrich GmbH & Co. KG (see table 1). Other than filament yarns based on glass or carbon fibers for instance a metal mesh allows a very specific set of properties like fiber diameter and mesh size (see Fig. 4). During processing no change in the shape of the circular cross-section is visible as well as no in-plane wire movement. The fiber diameter varies from 25 μm up to 630 μm , while the mesh size varies from 25 μm up to 1000 μm .

The materials are processed into organic sheets using a variothermic tool in a small scale static lab press. The diameter of the specimens is 50 mm. Therefore, reinforcement and matrix are cut into circular parts with a 50 mm diameter. The laminate stack is build up using one reinforcement layer to prevent any influence of multi-layer effects like nesting for example. The amount of matrix needed is calculated in terms of a most constant surface layer thickness. Figure 5 shows the base materials and the principal laminate stack and the positioning within the tool.

The process cycle is shown in figure 6. According to pre-trials the maximum temperature is set to 240 °C, which is 90 °C above the glass transition temperature of polycarbonate. The holding time at maximum temperature is 10 s. The pressure is linearly increased to 15 bar at maximum temperature and kept constant until the end of the manufacturing cycle. During the cooling stage a second holding temperature is set at 160 °C to allow relaxation processes within the system to reduce the overall internal stresses. From 160 °C to 25 °C the cooling rate is set to 67 °C/min.

Compared to standard organic sheets with filament yarn reinforcements the maximum temperature and holding time are set to low values. However, due to the lack of a micro-impregnation the metal fiber meshes are fully impregnated and there are no voids visible (see Fig. 7).

2.2 Characterization

The manufactured organic sheets were optically characterized by cross sectional light microscopy images to verify the impregnation quality and matrix surface layer thickness and white light profilometry to measure the surface waviness. Specimens were cut from two different positions on the laminate (see Fig. 8) to evaluate variations in surface layer thickness over diameter. Such variations may occur due to slightly uneven metal meshes and the possibility of tilted meshes during the manufacturing as the meshes are not fixed in z-direction. Specimens for light microscopy images were grinded and polished. The images are made using a Leica Aristoplan[®] with an attached CCD-camera.

To analyze the waviness white light profilometry measurements are conducted with a white light interferometer from FRT GmbH. Each specimen is measured two times on top and bottom side. To achieve constant statistical information the surface to be measured is set to 10 periods/meshes. Therefore, the overall measured area varies between the different laminates, but the more important waviness statistic is kept constant. To analyze waviness the collected data have to be divided into different characteristic regions, namely roughness and waviness. The characterization is done using FRT MarkIII[®] software from FRT GmbH. DIN EN ISO 4287 describes the waviness region in between the parameters λ_c and λ_f (see Fig. 9). The current FRT MarkIII software is only able to set a value for λ_c . The use of fabrics makes it possible to set a very distinct value for λ_c as we are dealing with very regular structures. Based on the simplified schematic drawing in Figure 2, one can calculate the wavelength λ_c as

$$\lambda_c = 2 \times r + w \quad (5)$$

where r is the fiber radius and w is the width between two fibers (see Fig.10).

To evaluate the surface quality the most important waviness value is the maximum waviness W_z . It

describes the maximum distance between a profile valley and a profile tip within a certain measurement distance. To calculate the maximum waviness W_z the measured area is divided into five equal areas. Then the mean value sW_z is calculated according to equation 6.

$$sW_z (DIN) = \frac{1}{5} \sum_{i=1}^5 W_z(i) \quad (6)$$

The division into 5 parts is explained historically, where only line scans were performed. The disadvantage when scanning areas is a preferred orientation (compare Fig. 12). Recent developments improve the waviness analysis by dividing the area into 25 equal areas. Any calculation induced anisotropic effects are eliminated. Equation 1 changes to

$$sW_z 25 = \frac{1}{25} \sum_{i=1}^5 \sum_{j=1}^5 W_z(i, j) \quad (7)$$

The maximum waviness W_z used in this paper is based on the $sW_z 25$ values.

3 Results

The calculation of maximum waviness with FRT MarkIII software is very sensitive to the critical wavelength λ_c and should ideally be set to the calculated value from equation 5. However, if the reinforcement geometry changes during processing smaller meshes would not be integrated in the waviness calculation. Figure 12 compares the influence of different λ_c values on the maximum waviness over fiber diameter for 9 fabric combinations. It can be seen that small differences in waviness values can be measured with variation of λ_c . The very regular and narrow mesh sizes did not change during manufacturing of the laminates. However, smaller critical wavelength values lead to slightly increased waviness values. To include minor changes in reinforcement geometry all further experiments were evaluated with the smaller critical wavelength $0.9 * \lambda_c$.

3.1 Textile parameters vs. surface waviness

One of the characteristic fabric parameters is the mesh size. To evaluate the influence of the mesh size on the waviness three pairs of fabrics with constant fiber diameter but varying mesh size were

characterized. It could be found that mesh size does not significantly influence the waviness creation (see Fig. 13). According to Kia the distance between rovings or fibers does not alter the amplitude of the waviness, which correspond to the maximum waviness, but only the wavelength of the characteristic surface texture [8]. It should be also kept in mind that the use of steel fibers leads to a very poor interphase, which is not capable of constraining the waviness creation due to internal interphase stresses.

According to equation 4 the maximum waviness corresponds directly to an increasing fiber diameter. To evaluate the influence of varying fiber diameters on the waviness four different fabrics with fiber diameters ranging from 110 to 250 μm were processed into organic sheets. All other laminate parameters like mesh size and surface layer thickness were kept constant. Figure 14 shows the maximum waviness over fiber diameter. With increasing fiber diameter the waviness values increase, as the total volume and height of matrix in the matrix rich regions is increasing.

3.2 Influence of polymer rheology on surface topology

Additionally, the theoretical maximum waviness over the whole temperature range $\Delta T = 215 \text{ K}$ is calculated taking into account the temperature induced shrinkage of the matrix as well as the steel fibers. The CTE of steel does not change within the used temperature range, while polycarbonate drastically changes its CTE around the glass transition temperature (T_g). Therefore, the calculations used two CTEs for PC, one below T_g and one above T_g [1]. When compared to the theoretical values for the whole temperature range the measured waviness values are much lower (see Fig. 15 and 16).

The hypothesis to explain this phenomenon is found in the rheological behavior of the polymer melt. As the press forces are applied perpendicular to the laminate surface the profile tips absorb most of the pressure. It is assumed that above T_g the matrix viscosity is able to reduce internal stress by volume flow towards the profile valleys and therefore compensating the waviness (see Fig. 17). The comparison between measured maximum waviness and theoretical waviness for the temperature range from T_g to room temperature is in good compliance

and supports the described theory. The deviation for the smallest mesh with a mesh and fiber diameter of 25 μm is explained by the resolution maximum of the white light profilometer, which is in the range of 300 nm (compare Fig. 18).

3.3 Influence of laminate build-up

In previous work the positive effect of increasing surface layer thicknesses on the waviness was simulated [1]. To evaluate the effect experiments with varying surface layer thickness were conducted. Figure 19 shows a decreasing waviness with increasing layer thickness. The results also support the theory of decreasing waviness during thermoforming due to compensating matrix flow above the glass transition temperature. According to the proposed theory a minimum surface layer thickness is necessary to allow compensating volume flow.

4 Summary

The paper deals with the topic of surface development during variothermic thermoforming of thermoplastic continuous fiber-reinforced composites. It comprises the influence of fiber diameter and mesh size as textile parameters on the maximum waviness and compares the measurements to theoretical waviness values. Within the characterized material systems the mesh size has no significant influences on the maximum waviness. With an increasing fiber diameter the maximum waviness increases. Experimental waviness values are compared to theoretical waviness values. As a result, a theory including the specific thermorheological properties of thermoplastics during thermoforming is proposed. Additionally, it is shown that an increasing surface layer thickness reduces the maximum waviness. Future work will focus on the development of a simulation tool that is capable of modeling polymer flow during thermoforming simulation.

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Table 1: List of used metal fiber meshes

Mesh size	Fiber diameter
w (mm)	d (µm)
0,025	25
0,050	40
0,063	40
0,080	50
0,100	80
0,200	125
0,250	200
0,315	110
0,315	160
0,315	200
0,315	250
0,400	250
0,500	320
1,000	630

Figure 1: Schematic drawing of waviness creation during processing

Figure 2: Simplified cross section A-A from Figure 1 with surface layer h_1

Figure 3: Surface roughness R_t against the stiffness of surface polymer layer [5]

Figure 4: Characteristic fabric properties yarn diameter d and mesh size w

Figure 5: Base materials and tool for organic sheet manufacturing (upper part) and schematic laminate build up

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Figure 6: Press program for specimen manufacturing

Figure 7: Cross-sectional images of two specimens with fully impregnated reinforcement structure

Figure 8: Positions from which the specimens were prepared of

Figure 9: Classification of wavelength regions into roughness (1) and waviness (2) [2]

Figure 10: The radius r and the spacing w between two rovings set the critical wavelength λ_c for waviness characterization

sWz (DIN)	sWz 25				
	Wz (1,1)	Wz (1,2)	Wz (1,3)	Wz (1,4)	Wz (1,5)
Wz (1)					
Wz (2)	Wz (1,2)	...			
Wz (3)	Wz (1,3)		...		
Wz (4)	Wz (1,4)			...	
Wz (5)	Wz (1,5)				...

Figure 11: Comparison of maximum waviness characterization with Wz and Wz25

Figure 12: Maximum waviness over fiber diameter with various minimum wavelengths L_c

Figure 13: Influence of different mesh sizes on maximum waviness

Figure 6: Maximum waviness over fiber diameter. An increasing fiber diameter leads to increased waviness

Figure 7: Comparison between theoretical and measured maximum waviness over fiber diameter

Figure 8: Comparison between theoretical and measured maximum waviness over fiber diameter

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Figure 9: Comparison of classic model and the proposed model including polymer flow above T_g

Figure 10: Surface topology obtained from white light profilometry measurements. Resolution maximum reached for the finest mesh size.

Figure 11: Maximum waviness over surface layer thickness. Increasing layer thickness decreases maximum waviness values.